

CRITICAL REVIEW OF VRANAPAHARI RAS IN THE CONSERVATIVE MANAGEMENT OF BHAGANDARA (ANAL FISTULA)

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ABSTRACT

Vranapahari Ras is a classical formulation described in Rasayogasagara^[1], composed of purified Parada, Gandhaka, Haratala, Manashila, Guggulu and Triphala, each employed only after appropriate Shodhana procedures. This formulation traditionally acclaimed by eminent Vaidyas, is recognised for its Vranaropana property and is widely available in the form of Gutika. It serves as a key constituent in various compound formulations. It is indicated in diverse pathological conditions such as Vrana, Nadivrana, Bhagandara where its therapeutic activity is attributed to its vrsya (rejuvenative), sothahara (anti-inflammatory), vranaropana (wound healing), kushtagna (anti-dermatotic) properties. This article attempts to provide a comprehensive understanding of probable mode of action and clinical relevance of Vranapahari Ras in the conservative management of Bhagandara.

KEYWORDS: Vranapahari Rasa, Bhagandara, Fistula-in-Ano.

INTRODUCTION

Bhagandara is one of the commonest diseases occurring in Ano-rectal region which is difficult to treat because of its high re-occurrence rates. The disease in which Bhaga, Guda and Basti Pradesa becomes Vidaarita (get torn) is known as Bhagandara. In Apakva-avastha it is known as Pidaka whereas in Pakva-avastha causes Bhagandara. In Ayurveda, Bhagandara has been

mentioned as one among Ashtamaharoga (eight major diseases) because of its callous attitude. Samhitas do have many evidences regarding the existence and treatment of Bhagandara.

The factors responsible for the cause of Bhagandara may be **Aharaja** (Kashaya rasa sevana, Ruksha Sevana Mithyaahara (ApathyaSevana), Asthi yukta ahara sevana, **Viharaja** (Excessive sexual activity, sitting in awkward position, forceful defecation, horse and elephant riding), **Agantuja** (trauma by krimi, trauma by asthi, improper use of vathi netra, manasika) factors.

CLASSIFICATION OF BHAGANDARA

Acharyas have classified Bhagandara on the basis of Dosha involvement and Samprapti (pathogenesis). According to Susrutha -

Types	Dosha	Feature	Discharge	Appearance
1. Shataponaka	Vata	Toda, Tadana, Chedana, Vyadhana, Gudadarana	Continuous Phenila Discharge	Water can or sieve-like multiple fistula
2. Ustragreeva	Pitta	Chosha pain like kshara or agni being applied to wound	Ushna And Durgandhitha Smelling	Camel's neck
3. Parisravi	Kapha	Kandu and less painful	Continuous And Slimy	whitish
4. Shambukavarta	Vata pitta	Toda, Daha, Kandu and migratory pain around anal canal	Multicolour	Tip of great toe, turns of conch
5. Unmargi/ Agantuja	Trauma To Rectum or Anal Canal	Kotha of mamsa and rakta infestation with krimi	Pus, feaces, urine, flatus, semen	No specific course of tract

- Madhava nidana^[2] has told 5 types of Bhagandara like Susrutha
- Astanga sangraha, Astanga Hrdaya^[3] and Sarangadhadhra^[4] have given 8 types of Bhagandara (parikshepi, riju, arso-bhagandara in addition to 5 types of bhagandara given by susrutha)
- According to Bhavaprakasha- Vatika, pattika, slashmika, sannipatika, shalyaja.^[5]

Bhagandara is considered as one of the Mahagada i.e. the disease that is difficult to cure. All types of Bhagandara are Krichchhsadhya (curable with difficulty) except Shambukavarta (Tridoshaja) and Unmargi (Agantuja), which are Asadhya (incurable).

Fistula-In-Ano: Fistula-In-Ano is an inflammatory tract, which has an external opening

(secondary opening) in the Peri-Anal skin and an internal opening (primary opening) in the anal canal or rectum. This track is lined by unhealthy granulation tissue and fibrous tissue and it is painful and can cause bleeding when you go to the toilet. Some fistulae can be connected to the sphincter muscles (the rings of muscles that open and close the anus).

Milligan and Morgan^[6] classified Fistulas into two based on their anatomical relationship with ano-rectal ring:

- Low fistula (The tract is situated below the level of anorectal ring and it is typically closer to the skin)
- High fistula (The tract extends atleast partially above the anorectal ring and it is typically situated deeper and may have longer tract)

Park^[7] classified the Fistulas into

- Inter-sphinctric
- Trans-sphincteric
- Supra-sphinctric
- Extra-sphinctric

CLINICAL FEATURES

- Swelling, Pain and discharge are the most frequent presenting complaints.
- Swelling and pain are usually associated with abscess when the external opening is closed.
- The discharge from the external opening is mucous or pus mixed with stool.
- In majority of cases of Anal fistula there will be an antecedent history of previous abscess.

Management of Bhagandara includes preventive measures, curative measures, surgical measures, adjuvant measures. In this article we'll discuss about conservative management of Anal Fistula with a compound formulation named Vranapahari Ras.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- Suddha Paradha -1part
- Suddha Gandhaka -2 parts
- Suddha Haritala -2 parts
- Suddha Manashila -2 parts
- Suddha Guggulu -7 parts

- Triphala Kwatha-Bhavana Dravya

1 part of Sudha paradha is triturated with two parts of sodhitha Gandhaka to obtain Kajjali, then it is added with 2 parts each of Manashila and Haratala. The above obtained paste is mixed with powder of 7 parts of suddha Guggulu. The obtained consistency is triturated (mardana) with Triphala kwatha for one day so that the consistency becomes semisolid paste like which can be further rolled into tablet (gutika) form of 2masha (1masha-0.972gm) each and stored in airtight container.^[8]

The word Suddha denotes that the drug has already undergone process of purification (shodhana) technique which is unique for each drug. Shodhana helps to remove any dosas (impurities/toxins) undesirable for humans from the drug. Even toxins from mineral ingredients are removed by proper shodhana.

PROPERTIES&MODE OF ACTION^[9]

PARADA: Hydrargyrum/quicksilver is the main ingredient in this formulation. It should be used only after proper shodhana and samskara. Parada sodhana mitigates all types of dosa (physical as well as chemical impurities) whereas the process of samskarana potentiates the mercury and renders it fit for all types of pharmaceutical and therapeutic purposes. It is used in the form of semisolid substance (natural occurrence) after removal of dosas and triturated or as bhasma (ash) after proper bhasma karma (method of preparing ash). Parada is Deepana (appetizer), pachana (carminative) vrsya (aphrodisiac), fast spreading. It balances metabolism, improves circulation in extremities and venous return. Parada also removes excess medodosa (adipose/cholesterol) and eliminates mala, mutra, sweda (excretory system metabolism).

GANDHAKA: It is the first mineral drug in uparasa group. It is a multivalent non-metal which is abundant in its native form. Sulphur is a yellow crystalline solid, which is odourless and tasteless. It is having properties like madhura rasa, katu vipaka, usna virya. It is Visagna, krimigna, deepana, pachana. Sulphur is essential for human metabolism. It is part of amino acid methionine and cysteine. It is indicated in Kandu, Kushta.

HARATALA: It is the fifth mineral drug of uparasa group. It is identified as orpiment or yellow arsenic. Chemically it is identified as Arsenic Trisulphide with chemical formula As_2S_3 . It has two varieties i.e. Patra haratala and Pinda haratala in which patra haratala should be used for therapeutic properties. It is tridosagna, useful in all twak vikaras, vrana, vatarakta

(gouty arthritis like). Haratala bhasma possess katu-kashaya rasa, usna virya, snigdha guna.

MANASHILA: It is the sixth mineral drug of uparasa group. It is identified as Realger which is reddish brown arsenic compound and chemically known as arsenic disulphide (As₂S₃). Unpurified compound is lethal and toxic. Use of properly purified compound (shodhana) results in good therapeutic benefits. Purified Manasila is having katu, tikta rasa with Snigdha, Usna, Guru guna. It exhibits Lekhana property. It is indicated in Agnimandhya, Ksaya, Anaha and Kandu. With wise use it acts as a rejuvenator (rasayana). It cures Jwara roga, improves the skin radiance (varnya), enhances virility and acts as antidote for visha in the body.

GUGGULU: It is Indian Bedellium known by scientific name Commiphora mukul. Guggulu is described as agnisthana and is used for Dhupa. In Atharva veda it is mentioned that yakshma and all other diseases will not spread to areas fumigated by Guggulu. During Samhita period guggulu is highly used for internal administration. The gummy resin extract is used in this formulation. Guggulu extract is considered purana (old) when it is more than 5years. Purana guggulu is having lekhana property^[10] while Nava (freshly extracted) Guggulu is having vrsya property. It is having katu tikta rasa, laghu ruksha, visada, sukshma, sara guna, usna virya, katu vipaka. It is tridosahara, rasayana. Guggulu is found effective against a wide variety of diseases like Medoroga, Amavata, Prameha, Asmari, Arshas, Kushta etc due to potential anti-inflammatory action of Guggulusterol (active principle).

TRIPHALA: It consists of three drugs- Harithaki (*Terminalia chebula*), Vibhithaki (*Terminalia bellarika*), Amalaka (*Embilica officinalis*). In all three drugs fruit rind is the useful part. Hence the name tri (three) phala (fruit).^[11] Triphala is having all rasas except lavana. Triphala have properties like tridosashamaka, shodhahara, vedhanahara, madhura vipaka, pramehagna. Dried powder of fruit rind is mixed together in equal proportion and is used as a single compound Triphala. Triphala along with ghrita in the formulation helps in better mobility of drugs in the body.

DISCUSSION

Vranapahari ras is formulated in such a way that potency of every ingredient is enhanced by the properties present in them. Parada helps in faster circulation of active ingredients to all parts of the body. Arsenics (Haratala, Manashila) have tikshana property which is balanced by Guggulu and Triphala during trituration. All the ingredients have rasayana property which

helps in faster wound healing and tissue regrowth in Bhagandara. Inflammation around the tissue is reduced due to the properties present in Guggulu and Triphala. The properties of Triphala is helpful in reducing discharge and slough formation in Bhagandara. The active principles of Haratala and Manashila is helpful for rapid wound contraction and tissue healing. In brief the total formulation is helpful in healing the wound and reduce inflammation which is present in Bhagandara.

CONCLUSION

The conservative management of Bhagandara, Madhyama Rogamarga disorder manifesting as Nadvrana in the Guda Pradesh—through the internal administration of Vranapahari Ras exemplifies the profound efficacy of Rasaushadhi Prayoga within Ayurveda. Rooted in the principles of Shamana Chikitsa and Dosha Pratyanka Upakrama, this approach targets the Sannipataja nature of Bhagandara, predominantly involving Pitta and Kapha Doshas, with Rakta and Mamsa Dhatu vitiation. Vranapahari Ras, endowed with Tikta, Katu Rasa, Laghu, Ruksha Guna, and Ushna Virya, acts as a potent Vranashodhaka, Vranaropaka, and Shothahara formulation. Its Deepana, Pachana, and Raktaprasadana properties facilitate Ama Pachana, Srotoshodhana, and Dhatu Samshodhana, thereby promoting Vrana Shuddhi and Vrana Ropana. The Rasayana effect of the formulation also supports Dhatu Pushti and enhances Ojas, contributing to systemic healing and immune modulation. It acts by faster healing of tissue and protection from pyogenic organisms in blood. This modality aligns with the classical teachings of Sushruta Samhita, which emphasize the importance of Yukti Vyapashraya Chikitsa in managing Dushta Vrana and Bhagandara. By integrating Rasaushadhi with Pathya-Apathya Niyama, Nitya Virechana, and Snehana-Swedana as adjunct therapies, the holistic management of Bhagandara becomes both effective and sustainable. Thus, Vranapahari Ras stands as a testament to the timeless wisdom of Ayurveda, offering a non-invasive, Sukha Sadhya pathway for healing a condition traditionally and along with kshara sutra, external dressing and wound care, Vranapahari ras can be administered in young and old and even in patients with systemic disorders like Diabetes mellitus and Hypertension. Vranapahari ras can also be administered along with vranaropana kasahayas.

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